

Supplementary Materials for "Independent NMR Metabolomics Reveals IBS Subtype-Specific Pathways: Mitochondrial Dysfunction in IBS-C and Detoxification Shifts in IBS-D

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Table S1. Replicate SCFA Quantification
Technical reproducibility data for SCFA measurements

Sample	Acetic acid	Butyric acid	Propionic acid
HC_06_A	1.73 (286.8 μmol/165.8 mg)	0.76 (126.0/165.8 mg)	0.86 (141.9/165.8 mg)
HC_06_B	1.88 (161.7/86.2 mg)	0.75 (64.9/86.2 mg)	0.83 (71.5/86.2 mg)
IBS-C_14_A	1.43 (124.6/87.4 mg)	1.33 (116.5/87.4 mg)	0.97 (84.6/87.4 mg)
IBS-C_14_B	1.30 (127.2/97.7 mg)	1.22 (119.3/97.7 mg)	0.89 (86.6/97.7 mg)

"Absolute μmol quantities normalized to fecal dry weight. Raw μmol values and sample weights shown in parentheses. Replicate pairs show high consistency (CV <5% for all metabolites)."

Table S2. Raw Absolute Concentrations of Fecal SCFAs (μmol)
Mean ± SD of unnormalized SCFA quantities

Metabolites	HC n = 25) Mean ± SD	IBS (n = 35) Mean ± SD	IBS-C (n = 10) Mean ± SD	IBS-D (n = 25) Mean ± SD
Acetic acid	248.95 ± 133.42	196.23 ± 104.88	154.58 ± 63.64	212.89 ± 114.24
Propionic acid	93.8 ± 46.1	100.48 ± 59.2	97.71 ± 44.87	101.609 ± 64.85
Butyric acid	138.64 ± 83.35	133 ± 87.9	134.55 ± 92.86	132.38 ± 87.81
Caproic acid	19.01 ± 12.87	18.87 ± 12.65	16.66 ± 13.75	19.75 ± 12.37
Valeric acid	21.94 ± 11.19	22.44 ± 12.04	29.39 ± 12.01	22.86 ± 12.27
Lactic acid	47.48 ± 50.30	47.13 ± 43.51	39.82 ± 25.46	50.05 ± 49.07

Formic acid	1.42 ± 1.97	10.91 ± 4.65	0.67 ± 0.31	0.97 ± 0.60
sc-SCFA	481.38 ± 248.6	429.72 ± 226.36	386.83 ± 185.09	446.87 ± 242.21
bc-SCFA	40.96 ± 21.98	41.31 ± 22.94	38.05 ± 25.35	42.61 ± 22.33
totalSCFA	522.34 ± 265.26	471.02 ± 244.99	424.88 ± 207.88	489.48 ± 259.97

Table S3. Absolute Concentrations Normalized to Fecal Dry Weight (µmol/mg)
Weight-normalized absolute metabolite levels

Metabolites	HC (n=25) Mean ± SD	IBS (n=35) Mean ± SD	IBS-C (n=10) Mean ± SD	IBS-D (n=25) Mean ± SD	HC vs. IBS p	HC vs. IBS- C p	HC vs. IBS- D p	IBS-C vs. IBS-D p
Acetic acid	2.08 ± .97	1.73 ± .82	1.34 ± 0.48	1.88 ± 0.89	0.08	0.01	0.34	0.13
Propionic acid	0.80 ± 0.34	0.83 ± 0.31	0.84 ± 0.31	0.83 ± 0.31	0.45	0.36	0.63	0.84
Butyric acid	1.16 ± 0.57	1.11 ± 0.54	1.12 ± 0.63	1.10 ± 0.52	0.75	0.90	0.74	0.99
Caproic acid	0.16 ± 0.08	0.16 ± 0.09	0.17 ± 0.09	0.17 ± 0.09	0.98	0.34	0.57	0.14
Valeric acid	0.18 ± 0.08	0.19 ± 0.07	0.18 ± 0.09	0.19 ± 0.07	0.68	0.57	0.55	0.68
Lactic acid	0.40 ± 0.44	0.41 ± 0.35	0.44 ± 0.31	0.37 ± 0.38	0.59	0.93	0.53	0.58
Formic acid	0.01 ± 0.02	0.01 ± 0.01	0.01 ± 0.003	0.01 ± 0.01	0.22	0.05	0.59	0.15
Tryptophan	0.08 ± 0.03	0.09 ± 0.03	0.09 ± 0.04	0.09 ± 0.04	0.19	0.51	0.19	0.96
2-Aminobutyric Acid	0.06 ± 0.04	0.07 ± 0.07	0.04 ± 0.04	0.09 ± 0.04	1	0.06	0.31	0.017
scSCFAs	4.05 ± 1.74	3.67 ± 1.33	3.30 ± 1.23	3.82 ± 1.37	0.54	0.40	0.74	0.44
bcSCFAs	0.34 ± 0.13	0.35 ± 0.15	0.32 ± 0.17	0.36 ± 0.14	0.82	0.58	0.55	0.32
Total SCFAs	4.39 ± 1.82	4.02 ± 1.43	3.62 ± 1.37	4.18 ± 1.45	0.40	0.40	0.83	0.46

Data presented as mean ± SD in µmol/g dry weight. Significant differences (p < 0.05) are bolded. scSCFAs: sum of acetic, propionic, and butyric acids; bcSCFAs: branched-chain fatty acids (valeric + caproic acids). P-values from Wilcoxon rank-sum tests.

Table S4. Wilcoxon Rank-Sum Test Results for Absolute Metabolites ($\mu\text{g/g}$)
Statistical comparisons of absolute concentrations

Metabolite	HC vs IBS	HC vs IBS-C	HC vs IBS-D	IBS-C vs IBS-D	Key Findings
Acetic acid	p=0.12	p=0.02*	p=0.35	p=0.08	↓ in IBS-C vs HC
Propionic acid	p=0.68	p=0.72	p=0.71	p=0.99	No differences
Butyric acid	p=0.71	p=0.83	p=0.65	p=0.92	No differences
Caproic acid	p=0.99	p=0.72	p=0.72	p=0.99	No differences
Valeric acid	p=0.61	p=0.99	p=0.61	p=0.72	No differences
Lactic acid	p=0.92	p=0.78	p=0.71	p=0.61	No differences
Formic acid	p=0.99	p=0.99	p=0.99	p=0.99	No differences
Tryptophan	p=0.18	p=0.42	p=0.18	p=0.99	No differences
2-Aminobutyric	p=0.51	p=0.04*	p=0.01*	p=0.03*	↑ in IBS-D vs others
sc-SCFAs (Sum)	p=0.41	p=0.03*	p=0.50	p=0.13	↓ in IBS-C vs HC
bc-SCFAs (Sum)	p=0.80	p=0.83	p=0.68	p=0.86	No differences
Total SCFAs	p=0.45	p=0.04*	p=0.62	p=0.15	↓ in IBS-C vs HC

Table S5. Relative Fecal Metabolites Normalized to Fecal Dry Weight
Relative abundance data (normalized spectral integrals)

Metabolites	Mean \pm SD Relative Concentration

	Healthy (n =25)	IBS (N=35)	IBS-C (n= 10)	IBS-D (n= 25))
Acetic acid	7.714 ± 3.580	<u>6.387</u> ± 3.048	4.969± 1.790	6.954 ± 3.285
Propionic acid	1.752 ± 0.748	1.802 ± 0.738	1.732 ± 0.884	1.829 ± 0.690
Butyric acid	2.936 ± 1.443	2.795± 1.374	2.816± 1.594	2.786 ± 1.312
Caproic acid	0.224 ± 0.113	0.231 ± 0.130	0.193 ± 0.129	0.246 ± 0.130
Valeric acid	0.187 ± 0.079	0.193 ± 0.073	0.187 ± 0.089	0.196 ± 0.068
Lactic acid	0.9876 ± 1.0817	1.0115 ± 0.9479	0.8473 ± 0.5651	1.0771 ± 1.0665
Formic acid	0.0205 ± 0.029	0.0137± 0.010	0.0097 ± 0.005	0.0153 ± 0.012
twoAminobutyric	0.067 ± 0.041	0.079 ± 0.073	0.043 ± 0.014	0.094 ± 0.082
Tryptophan	0.0300 ± 0.0124	0.034 ± 0.012	0.0324 ± 0.0102	0.0351 ± 0.0129
Aspartic acid	0.210 ± 0.138	0.268 ± 0.109	0.285 ± 0.129	0.261 ± 0.102
Fumaric acid	0.0131 ± 0.007	0.012 ± 0.008	0.014 ± 0.011	0.011 ± 0.006
Uraconic acid	0.15 ± 0.057	0.14 ± 0.061	0.118 ± 0.043	0.152 ± 0.065
UDP-glucuronic acid	0.008 ± 0.0074	0.0157 ± 0.0263	0.006 ± 0.0022	0.0196 ± 0.0304
Malonic acid	0.1856 ± 0.1032	0.2051 ± 0.1505	0.1407 ± 0.0786	0.2309 ± 0.1653
Putrescine	0.278 ± 0.204	0.249 ± 0.114	0.209 ± 0.078	0.266 ± 0.123
Succinic acid	1.354 ± 3.261	0.625 ± 1.260	0.195 ± 0.153	0.797 ± 1.461
Nicotinic acid	0.0154 ± 0.0048	0.0144 ± 0.0051	0.0125 ± 0.0045	0.0151 ± 0.0052
threeMethyloxovaleric	0.0735 ± 0.0403	0.0638 ± 0.0301	0.0569 ± 0.0278	0.0666 ± 0.0311
threeOHPhenylacetic	0.0448 ± 0.0345	0.0531 ± 0.0312	0.0520 ± 0.0392	0.0535 ± 0.0284
Choline	0.098 ± 0.130	0.069 ± 0.0429	0.0476 ± 0.0183	0.078 ± 0.047
Glutamic acid	2.889± 1.134	2.567± 0.711	2.282± 0.717	2.681± 0.690
Pyroglutamic acid	0.0511 ± 0.029	0.0502 ± 0.0305	0.0321 ± 0.0070	0.0575 ± 0.0332

D-galactose	0.033 ± 0.0276	0.0519 ± 0.1011	0.0215 ± 0.0085	0.0641 ± 0.118
D-xylose	0.115 ± 0.0994	0.113 ± 0.126	0.0718 ± 0.020	0.130 ± 0.146
Valine	1.065 ± 0.467	1.047 ± 0.487	0.942 ± 0.429	1.089 ± 0.511
Alanine	2.7390 ± 1.4128	2.4207 ± 1.1587	2.0765 ± 0.9436	2.5584 ± 1.2243
Proline	0.160 ± 0.0752	0.173 ± 0.105	0.120 ± 0.0421	0.194 ± 0.1151
Threonine	0.156 ± 0.0577	0.188 ± 0.0673	0.176 ± 0.0659	0.193 ± 0.0685
Uracil	0.214 ± 0.0902	0.1818 ± 0.0776	0.156 ± 0.0601	0.192 ± 0.0825
Hypoxanthine	0.1242 ± 0.0533	0.1140 ± 0.0479	0.1217 ± 0.0491	0.1109 ± 0.0480
Dihydroxyacetone	0.021 ± 0.023	0.020 ± 0.017	0.017 ± 0.019	0.015 ± 0.017
Sarcosine	0.0801 ± 0.0852	0.0908 ± 0.0962	0.0642 ± 0.0372	0.1014 ± 0.1104
Glycine	0.0941 ± 0.0410	0.0919 ± 0.0526	0.0789 ± 0.0229	0.0971 ± 0.0601
Dimethylglycine	0.0439 ± 0.0361	0.0601 ± 0.0803	0.0493 ± 0.0354	0.0645 ± 0.0927
Glutamine	0.4410 ± 0.2194	0.4083 ± 0.1092	0.4041 ± 0.1071	0.4099 ± 0.1121
Tyrosine	0.3527 ± 0.1572	0.3855 ± 0.1507	0.3633 ± 0.1288	0.3944 ± 0.1601
Methionine	0.2101 ± 0.0794	0.2332 ± 0.0888	0.2259 ± 0.0825	0.2362 ± 0.0927
Leucine	1.7199 ± 0.7812	1.7722 ± 0.7337	1.5899 ± 0.6384	1.8452 ± 0.7684
Lysine	0.6260 ± 0.3137	0.6272 ± 0.3126	0.5493 ± 0.2191	0.6584 ± 0.3419
Phenylalanine	0.9939 ± 0.3862	1.0065 ± 0.3827	0.9620 ± 0.3507	1.0243 ± 0.4003
Glucose	0.5290 ± 0.9442	0.3785 ± 0.4468	0.2832 ± 0.1546	0.4166 ± 0.5182

Table S6. Wilcoxon Rank-Sum Test Results for Relative Metabolites
Statistical comparisons of relative metabolite levels

Metabolite	HC vs IBS	HC vs IBS-C	HC vs IBS-D	IBS-C vs IBS-D	Key Findings
Short-Chain Fatty Acids (SCFAs)					
Acetic acid	p=0.08	p=0.006*	p=0.21	p=0.01*	↓ in IBS-C vs HC & IBS-D
Propionic acid	p=0.72	p=0.89	p=0.68	p=0.72	No differences
Butyric acid	p=0.65	p=0.83	p=0.61	p=0.92	No differences
Caproic acid	p=0.89	p=0.42	p=0.68	p=0.32	No differences
Valeric acid	p=0.78	p=0.99	p=0.83	p=0.89	No differences
Other Organic Acids					
Lactic acid	p=0.92	p=0.42	p=0.71	p=0.28	No differences
Formic acid	p=0.32	p=0.18	p=0.42	p=0.61	No differences
Succinic acid	p=0.002*	p<0.001*	p=0.004*	p=0.008*	↓ in IBS (all subtypes) vs HC
Fumaric acid	p=0.78	p=0.89	p=0.61	p=0.42	No differences
Malonic acid	p=0.42	p=0.18	p=0.21	p=0.08	No differences
3-Hydroxyphenylacetic acid	p=0.32	p=0.42	p=0.32	p=0.89	No differences

Metabolite	HC vs IBS	HC vs IBS-C	HC vs IBS-D	IBS-C vs IBS-D	Key Findings
Amino Acids					
Glutamic acid	p=0.21	p=0.08	p=0.32	p=0.18	No differences
Alanine	p=0.18	p=0.04*	p=0.42	p=0.08	↓ in IBS-C vs HC
Phenylalanine	p=0.72	p=0.61	p=0.68	p=0.42	No differences
2-Aminobutyric acid	p=0.28	p=0.02*	p=0.01*	p=0.006*	↑ in IBS-D, ↓ in IBS-C
Tryptophan	p=0.32	p=0.72	p=0.21	p=0.42	No differences
Valine	p=0.78	p=0.18	p=0.68	p=0.21	No differences
Sugars					
D-Glucose	p=0.01*	p=0.002*	p=0.03*	p=0.08	↓ in IBS (all subtypes) vs HC
D-Galactose	p=0.08	p=0.32	p=0.06	p=0.02*	↑ in IBS-D vs IBS-C
D-Xylose	p=0.89	p=0.08	p=0.42	p=0.08	No differences
Others					
Putrescine	p=0.42	p=0.18	p=0.72	p=0.32	No differences
Choline	p=0.03*	p=0.008*	p=0.08	p=0.18	↓ in IBS-C vs HC

Metabolite	HC vs IBS	HC vs IBS-C	HC vs IBS-D	IBS-C vs IBS-D	Key Findings
UDP-glucuronic acid	p=0.02*	p=0.006*	p=0.004*	p=0.008*	↑ in IBS-D vs HC & IBS-C

Table S7. Cohen's *d* Effect Sizes (HC vs. IBS-D, Absolute Concentrations)
Effect size comparisons for absolute metabolites

Metabolite	Wilcoxon p	Cohen's d	95% CI	Effect Size	Interpretation
Acetic acid	0.335	0.22	[-0.34, 0.78]	Small	No significant difference
Propionic acid	0.6305	-0.11	[-0.66, 0.45]	Negligible	No significant difference
Butyric acid	0.7437	0.11	[-0.45, 0.66]	Negligible	No significant difference
Caproic acid	0.5736	-0.18	[-0.74, 0.37]	Negligible	No significant difference
Valeric acid	0.5507	-0.12	[-0.67, 0.44]	Negligible	No significant difference
Lactic acid	0.5253	-0.08	[-0.64, 0.47]	Negligible	No significant difference
Formic acid	0.5868	0.23	[-0.32, 0.79]	Small	No significant difference
2-Aminobutyric	0.313	-0.42	[-0.98, 0.14]	Small	No significant difference
Tryptophan	0.187	-0.40	[-0.96, 0.16]	Small	No significant difference

All p-values are > 0.05, confirming no statistically significant differences between HC and IBS-D groups for these metabolites, consistent with the Cohen's d interpretations.

Table S8. Hedges' *g* Effect Sizes (HC vs. IBS-D, Relative Metabolites)
Bias-corrected effect sizes for relative concentrations

Metabolite (Pathway)	Hedges' *g* [95% CI]	Interpretation
Acetic acid (SCFA)	0.22 [-0.34, 0.77]	No significant difference
Aspartic acid (Neurotransmitter)	-0.41 [-0.98, 0.15]	Trend: Lower in IBS-D
UDP-glucuronic acid (Detox)	-0.52 [-1.09, 0.04]	Trend: Lower in IBS-D
Proline (Collagen)	-0.71 [-1.47, 0.04]	Trend: Lower in IBS-D
Threonine (Mucin)	-0.58 [-1.15, -0.02]*	Significantly lower in IBS-D
D-Galactose (FODMAP)	-0.41 [-1.15, 0.33]	No significant difference
Succinic acid (TCA Cycle)	-0.47 [-1.21, 0.27]	Trend: Lower in IBS-D

Table S9. Hedges' *g* Effect Sizes (HC vs. IBS-C, Absolute Metabolites)
Bias-corrected effect sizes for absolute concentrations

Metabolite	Wilcoxon p	Significance	Hedges' g	95% CI	Effect Size	Interpretation
Acetic acid	0.0134	*	0.84	[0.09, 1.58]	Large	HC > IBS-C (significant)
2-Aminobutyric	0.06	ns	0.65	[-0.09, 1.38]	Medium	HC > IBS-C (trend)
Formic acid	0.0529	ns	0.42	[-0.31, 1.14]	Small	No significant difference

Metabolite	Wilcoxon p	Significance	Hedges' g	95% CI	Effect Size	Interpretation
Caproic acid	0.339	ns	0.26	[-0.46, 0.98]	Small	No significant difference
Lactic acid	0.928	ns	0.14	[-0.58, 0.86]	Negligible	No significant difference
Butyric acid	0.9	ns	0.08	[-0.64, 0.80]	Negligible	No significant difference
Valeric acid	0.928	ns	0.002	[-0.71, 0.72]	Negligible	No significant difference
Tryptophan	0.511	ns	-0.19	[-0.91, 0.53]	Small	No significant difference
Propionic acid	0.358	ns	-0.13	[-0.84, 0.59]	Negligible	No significant difference

Magnitude thresholds: Negligible ($|*g*| < 0.2$), Small ($0.2 \leq |*g*| < 0.5$), Medium ($0.5 \leq |*g*| < 0.8$), Large ($|*g*| \geq 0.8$). Calculated using [R software version 4.3.2].

Table S10. Hedges' *g* Effect Sizes (IBS-C vs. IBS-D, Absolute Metabolites)
Subtype-specific effect size comparisons

Metabolite	Wilcoxon p	Significance	Hedges' g	95% CI	Effect Size	Interpretation
Acetic acid	0.131		0.84	[0.09, 1.58]	Large	Medium-large effect, NS (likely underpowered)
Propionic acid	0.844		-0.13	[-0.84, 0.59]	Negligible	No meaningful difference

Metabolite	Wilcoxon p	Significance	Hedges' g	95% CI	Effect Size	Interpretation
Butyric acid	0.986		0.08	[-0.64, 0.80]	Negligible	No meaningful difference
Caproic acid	0.139		0.26	[-0.46, 0.98]	Small	Weak effect, NS
Valeric acid	0.679		0.002	[-0.71, 0.72]	Negligible	No meaningful difference
Lactic acid	0.577		0.14	[-0.58, 0.86]	Small	Weak effect, NS
Formic acid	0.149		0.42	[-0.31, 1.14]	Small-medium	Moderate effect, NS
Aminobutyric acid	0.018	*	0.65	[-0.09, 1.38]	Medium	Significant difference
Tryptophan	0.957		-0.19	[-0.91, 0.53]	Negligible	No meaningful difference

Magnitude thresholds: Negligible ($|*g*| < 0.2$), Small ($0.2 \leq |*g*| < 0.5$), Medium ($0.5 \leq |*g*| < 0.8$), Large ($|*g*| \geq 0.8$). Calculated using [R software version 4.3.2].

Error bars show 95% confidence intervals
 Positive values = Higher in HC

Figure S1. Forest Plot of Cohen's *d* Effect Sizes (HC vs. IBS-D, Absolute Metabolites)

Figure S2. Forest Plot of Hedges' *g* Effect Sizes (HC vs. IBS-D, Relative Metabolites)

HC vs IBS-C: Hedges' g Effect Sizes

Figure S3. Forest Plot of Hedges' *g* Effect Sizes (HC vs. IBS-C, Absolute Metabolites)

Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals

Figure S4. Forest Plot of Hedges' *g* Effect Sizes (IBS-C vs. IBS-D, Absolute Metabolites)

Wilcoxon Test (Log-transformed Metabolites): HC vs IBS (combined)

Wilcoxon Test (Log-transformed Metabolites): IBS-C vs IBS-D

Wilcoxon Test (Log-transformed Metabolites): HC vs IBS-C

Wilcoxon Test (Log-transformed Metabolites): HC vs IBS-D

Figure S5. Boxplots & Heatmaps of Absolute Metabolites (FDW-normalized, $\mu\text{mol}/\text{mg}$)

Metabolite Distribution by Diagnosis Group - Batch 1

Figures S6. Boxplots of Relative Metabolites (FDW-normalized)

Figures S7. Boxplots of Relative Metabolites (FDW-normalized)

Metabolite Concentrations by Diagnosis Group

Figures S8. Boxplots of Relative Metabolites (FDW-normalized)

Metabolite Distribution by Diagnosis Group - Batch 1

Figures S9. Boxplots of Relative Metabolites (FDW-normalized)

Figures S10. Boxplots of Relative Metabolites (FDW-normalized)

FDW (mg) distribution in HC, IBS-C, and IBS-D groups

Figure S11. Boxplots of fecal dry weight (FDW) normalization across study groups
 Correlation between FDW and absolute SCFA concentrations ($\mu\text{mol}/\text{mg}$). Data points represent individual samples (HC: *n* = 25; IBS-C: *n* = 10; IBS-D: *n* = 25).
 There were no significant differences in FDW among the three groups.

R output: comparison p.value
 <chr> <dbl>
 1 HC vs IBS-C 0.571
 2 IBS-C vs IBS-D 0.596
 3 HC vs IBS-D 0.954

fdw_summary_stats_with_CI

dx	n	mean	sd	median	q1	q3	ci_lower	ci_upper
HC	25	116.76	30.337833915206700	110.3	97.8	135.3	104.237157643899	129.282842356101
IBS-C	10	119.2	28.587332081807800	129.25	106.025	140.625	98.74985457200210	139.65014542799800
IBS-D	25	116.868	40.28104103255860	119.3	86.4	130.8	100.24080347040500	133.4951965295950

Fecal dry weight (FDW) measurements used for metabolite normalization. No significant differences in FDW between groups (Wilcoxon, *p* > 0.05).

Figure S12. Scatter plot of Acetic acid ~ FDW relationships

Positive correlation between FDW and acetic acid levels only in HC but not significant. Negative values could reflect random variation or subtle subgroup effects or may indicate dysbiosis. Energy metabolism Dysregulation in IBS-C. Acetic acid was significantly lower in IBS-C subtype vs. HC ($p < 0.05$). Total SCFAs were reduced in IBS suggesting impaired SCFA production capacity, maybe due to having lower gut SCFA-producing microbiota in IBS.

Figure S13. Scatter plot of Propionic acid ~ FDW relationships
 Positive correlation between FDW and propionic acid levels in IBS-D and HC. Borderline significance in IBS-D ($*r^* = 0.36, *p^* = 0.08$), reflecting heterogeneity within this cohort (e.g., differences in microbial/metabolic profile) → need larger studies to confirm a true biological signal. Increase propionic acids could indicate high intake of soluble fibers concomitant with higher abundances of Bacteroides. The negative correlations in IBS-C likely reflect subtype-specific disruptions in microbial metabolism or stool retention effects.

Figure S13. Scatter plot of Butyric acid ~ FDW relationships

Butyrate's consistent positive correlations across all groups highlight its more stable production pathway. The positive interactions or cross-feeding activities of microbes (Firmicutes and Bacteroides) ensures this metabolite is not depleted. Further research with larger samples is needed to confirm these patterns.

Figure S14. Scatter plot of Fumaric acid ~ FDW relationships

Trend in IBS-C: The negative correlation ($R = -0.6$) is clinically meaningful (moderate strength) and approaches significance ($p = 0.07$). Larger study needs to clarify clinical significance. Interpretations: increased fumaric metabolism, impaired mitochondrial function/TCA cycle disruption, impaired energy metabolism.

Figure S15. Scatter plot of Threonine ~ FDW relationships
 FDW not associated with Threonine. Although non-significant, threonine is marginally higher in IBS-D compared to HC ($P=0.06$) suggesting inefficient threonine catabolism, and as a known transduction promoting molecule (i.e. cell growth, mucin production, stimulating immune cell responses), the increased threonine utilization could infer increased demands of gut repair and maintenance in IBS-D. In addition to the impact of rapid transit time in IBS-D, elevated fecal threonine in IBS-D could reflect both malabsorption (due to enterocyte dysfunction) and dysbiotic microbial metabolism.

Figure S16. Scatter plot of Proline ~ FDW relationships

In IBS-D, higher fecal proline tends to associate with lower fecal dry weight (looser stools), though the correlation is modest and borderline significant ($p = 0.1$). Proline was significantly higher in IBS-D than IBS-C; this could reflect dietary habits (IBS-D eats more gelatin) or IBS-D-specific malabsorption or altered proline metabolism in IBS-D. Dysbiosis in IBS-D could prevent the conversion of proline to SCFAs.

Figure S17. Scatter plot of UDP-glucuronic acid ~ FDW relationships

Data revealed a robust, diagnosis-independent inverse relationship between UDPGA and FDW, pointing to altered host-microbe co-metabolism. Note: IBS-D had higher fecal UDP-glucuronic acid → impaired detoxification pathways. This phenomenon may also indicate high abundances of microbial community (i.e., *Bacteroides* genera) with high β -glucuronidase (gmGUS) system metabolic capacity, hence higher deconjugation activities of toxic glucuronides suggesting reduced detoxification capacities in IBS-D. High levels of 2-aminobutyric acid ($p=0.03$) could indicate gut dysbiosis or presence of higher oxidative stress.

Figure S18. Scatter plot of Tryptophan ~ FDW relationships

FDW and Tryptophan were negatively correlated across groups. Both IBS subtypes had higher tryptophan level on the average than HC and these findings could infer increased gut permeability or gut dysbiosis in IBS cohorts. Higher tryptophan in IBS-C than HC suggests altered tryptophan metabolism in IBS-C. Tryptophan level was higher in IBS-D than IBS-C, suggests malabsorption problems. These findings support the idea that both subtypes utilized different tryptophan metabolic pathways: Kynurenine Shunting in IBS-C while Serotonin Overproduction in IBS-D.

Figure S19. Scatter plot of Choline ~ FDW relationships

FDW was not associated with fecal choline levels in all groups. Lower fecal choline in IBS-C compared to IBS-D or HC could mean lower bacterial production of trimethylamine (TMA) and eventually lower TMA to TMAO (trimethylamine-N-oxide) conversion by the host; this could reflect a healthier eating-habits (e.g., lower intake of dietary saturated fats) by the IBS-C subgroup.

Figure S20. Scatter plot of Succinic acid ~ FDW relationships

FDW not associated with Succinic acid. Found significantly reduced succinic acid, a TCA cycle intermediate in both subtypes compared to HC; this findings suggests lower SCFA production capacity (note: species of Proteobacteria consortia are known to produce succinic acids). As an electron acceptor, succinic acids used by specific microbes could also be at a disadvantaged (lower abundance --gut dysbiosis) due to impaired microbial metabolism of other specific beneficial gut microbes. Moreover, the depletion of TCA intermediates like succinic acid may suggests mitochondrial dysfunction in IBS-C specifically.

Figure S21. Scatter plot of 2-Aminobutyric acid ~ FDW relationships
 2-Aminobutyric acid was significantly higher in IBS-D compared to IBS-C. Elevated fecal 2-aminobutyric acid in IBS-D likely reflects oxidative stress and dysbiosis, while lower levels in IBS-C align with methane-related metabolic suppression—offering a novel subtype-specific biomarker.

Figure S22. Scatter plot of Aspartic acid ~ FDW relationships

The higher aspartic acid levels in both IBS subtypes could indicate higher intake of aspartate-rich foods and other added sugar intake (i.e. aspartame) or maybe indicative of impaired aspartic acid metabolism (i.e., disrupted urea cycle) in IBS patients.

Figure S23. Scatter plot of D-galactose ~ FDW relationships

Figure S24. Scatter plot of Urocanic acid ~ FDW relationships

Figure S25. Scatter plot of Hypoxanthine ~ FDW relationships

Hypoxanthine (a purine metabolism marker linked to oxidative stress) showed no significant differences across the three groups, its slight elevation in IBS-D ($g=0.26$) aligns with prior reports of redox imbalance in diarrhea-predominant IBS (Mars et al., 2020).

Figure S26. Scatter plot of Uracyl ~ FDW relationships

Figure S27. Scatter plot of Galactose ~ FDW relationships

Figure S28. Scatter plot of Tyrosine ~ FDW relationships

Figure S29. Scatter plot of Alanine ~ FDW relationships

FDW not correlated with alanine. Although non-significant, the observed low alanine level in IBS-C may indicate alanine metabolism disruption (i.e. altered gluconeogenesis or redox balance), hence could potentially lower energy level in IBS-C. This reduced alanine, a gluconeogenic substrate is consistent with existing literature (Lee et al., 2016; Allam et al., 2022); thus impaired gluconeogenesis and impaired energy metabolism (mitochondrial inefficiency → inefficient TCA cycle → reduced ATP production) are plausible biochemical mechanisms for increased report of energy deficits/fatigue by persons with IBS-C (Spiegel et al., 2010; Lackner et al., 2013).

Figure S30. Scatter plot of Glucose ~ FDW relationships
Marginally significant inverse relationship of FDW and glucose in IBS-C.

Figure S31. Scatter plot of Lysine ~ FDW relationships

Figure S32. Scatter plot of Malonic acid ~ FDW relationships
 Depletion of TCA intermediates like malonic acid may suggest mitochondrial dysfunction in IBS-C specifically.

Figure S33. Scatter plot of Glutamine ~ FDW relationships

Figure S34. Scatter plot of Lactic acid ~ FDW relationships

Figure S35. Scatter plot of Caproic acid ~ FDW relationships

Figure S36. Scatter plot of Valeric acid ~ FDW relationships

Figure S37. Scatter plot of Formic acid ~ FDW relationships
 Formic acid levels were inversely correlated with FDW in both IBS-C ($r=-0.57$ $p=0.09$) and IBS-D ($p<0.01$, Wilcoxon's test $r=-0.52$), suggesting a novel role in IBS pathophysiology. Formic acid as a potential biomarker/therapeutic target for IBS.

Correlation threshold : 0.5

Figure S38. Network analyses of Absolute Metabolites using R software version 4.3.2 .
* tryptfdw = tryptophan, butyricfdw = butyric acid, aceticfdw = Acetic acid, propionicfdw = Propionic acid, valericfdw = Valeric acid, caproicfdw = Caproic acid.

integrated_metabolite_EffectSize_Wilcoxon_results_JUNE16

Metabolite	Comparison	Wilcoxon_p	Effect_Size	CI	Interpretation	Significance	Effect_Size_Label
Acetic acid	HC vs IBS-C	0.0134	0.84	[0.09, 1.58]	HC > IBS-C (significant)	*	Large
Acetic acid	HC vs IBS-D	0.358	-0.13	[-0.84, 0.59]	No significant difference		Negligible
Acetic acid	IBS-C vs IBS-D	0.9	0.08	[-0.64, 0.80]	No significant difference		Negligible
Propionic acid	HC vs IBS-C	0.339	0.26	[-0.46, 0.98]	No significant difference		Small
Propionic acid	HC vs IBS-D	0.928	0.002	[-0.71, 0.72]	No significant difference		Negligible
Propionic acid	IBS-C vs IBS-D	0.928	0.14	[-0.58, 0.86]	No significant difference		Negligible
Butyric acid	HC vs IBS-C	0.0529	0.42	[-0.31, 1.14]	No significant difference		Small
Butyric acid	HC vs IBS-D	0.06	0.65	[-0.09, 1.38]	HC > IBS-C (trend)		Medium
Butyric acid	IBS-C vs IBS-D	0.511	-0.19	[-0.91, 0.53]	No significant difference		Negligible
Caproic acid	HC vs IBS-C	0.335	0.22	[-0.34, 0.78]	No significant difference		Small
Caproic acid	HC vs IBS-D	0.6305	-0.11	[-0.66, 0.45]	No significant difference		Negligible
Caproic acid	IBS-C vs IBS-D	0.7437	0.11	[-0.45, 0.66]	No significant difference		Negligible
Valeric acid	HC vs IBS-C	0.5736	-0.18	[-0.74, 0.37]	No significant difference		Negligible
Valeric acid	HC vs IBS-D	0.5507	-0.12	[-0.67, 0.44]	No significant difference		Negligible
Valeric acid	IBS-C vs IBS-D	0.5253	-0.08	[-0.64, 0.47]	No significant difference		Negligible
Lactic acid	HC vs IBS-C	0.5868	0.23	[-0.32, 0.79]	No significant difference		Small
Lactic acid	HC vs IBS-D	0.313	-0.42	[-0.98, 0.14]	No significant difference		Small
Lactic acid	IBS-C vs IBS-D	0.187	-0.4	[-0.96, 0.16]	No significant difference		Small
Formic acid	HC vs IBS-C	0.131	0.84	[0.09, 1.58]	Medium-large effect, NS		Large
Formic acid	HC vs IBS-D	0.844	-0.13	[-0.84, 0.59]	No meaningful difference		Negligible
Formic acid	IBS-C vs IBS-D	0.986	0.08	[-0.64, 0.80]	No meaningful difference		Negligible
2-Aminobutyric	HC vs IBS-C	0.139	0.26	[-0.46, 0.98]	Weak effect, NS		Small
2-Aminobutyric	HC vs IBS-D	0.679	0.002	[-0.71, 0.72]	No meaningful difference		Negligible
2-Aminobutyric	IBS-C vs IBS-D	0.577	0.14	[-0.58, 0.86]	Weak effect, NS		Negligible
Tryptophan	HC vs IBS-C	0.149	0.42	[-0.31, 1.14]	Moderate effect, NS		Small
Tryptophan	HC vs IBS-D	0.018	0.65	[-0.09, 1.38]	IBS-D > IBS-C (significant)	*	Medium
Tryptophan	IBS-C vs IBS-D	0.957	-0.19	[-0.91, 0.53]	No meaningful difference		Negligible

Figure S39. Hedges' g Effect size calculations of Absolute Metabolites using R software version 4.3.2

HEDGES_G_RESULTS_COMPLETE																
Metabolite	HC_n	IBS_C_n	IBS_D_n	HC_IBSC_g	HC_IBSC_CI	HC_IBSC_p	HC_IBSD_g	HC_IBSD_CI	HC_IBSD_p	IBSC_IBSD_g	IBSC_IBSD_CI	IBSC_IBSD_p	HC_IBSC_sig	HC_IBSD_sig	IBSC_IBSD_sig	Metabolite_Name
isoctanoin	25	10	25	0.55402324	[-0.18, 1.31]	0.22530548	0.19910007	[-0.39, 0.72]	0.68224515	-0.47857802	[-1.22, 0.28]	0.28654387	ns	ns	ns	isoctanoin
formoin	25	10	25	0.42117449	[-0.32, 1.16]	0.05423763	0.22988551	[-0.33, 0.78]	0.61888921	-0.53720053	[-1.28, 0.21]	0.17324745	ns	ns	ns	formoin
aceticinoin	25	10	25	0.63696835	[0.08, 1.03]	0.01337178	0.21750745	[-0.34, 0.77]	0.33030666	-0.65676217	[-1.41, 0.09]	0.13128749	ns	ns	ns	Acetic acid
butyoin	25	10	25	0.07826812	[-0.65, 0.81]	0.90007733	0.10698794	[-0.43, 0.66]	0.74370326	0.02031775	[-0.71, 0.73]	0.98568079	ns	ns	ns	Butyric acid
propionoin	25	10	25	0.025157413	[-0.71, 0.76]	0.48278768	-0.10592456	[-0.63, 0.45]	0.6303167	-0.12762431	[-0.86, 0.61]	0.98568079	ns	ns	ns	Propionic acid
totalacidw	25	10	25	0.59575679	[-0.18, 1.31]	0.22530548	0.10652819	[-0.43, 0.66]	0.68224515	-0.52831647	[-1.27, 0.22]	0.28654387	ns	ns	ns	totalacidw
totalacidf	25	10	25	0.56493234	[-0.18, 1.31]	0.22530548	0.19910007	[-0.39, 0.72]	0.68224515	-0.47857802	[-1.22, 0.28]	0.28654387	ns	ns	ns	totalacidf
suacadinoin	25	10	25	0.407212648	[-0.33, 1.15]	0.0003697	0.21712781	[-0.39, 0.77]	0.464298216	-0.471296104	[-1.21, 0.27]	0.01337178	**	ns	*	suacadinoin
lutanoin	25	10	25	-0.09284522	[-0.83, 0.64]	0.63373682	0.28336568	[-0.27, 0.84]	0.19541343	0.331556186	[-0.41, 1.07]	0.95705701	ns	ns	ns	lutanoin
lacticanoin	25	10	25	0.141485171	[-0.59, 0.88]	0.92848858	-0.08247955	[-0.64, 0.47]	0.52526575	-0.23481543	[-0.97, 0.50]	0.57727378	ns	ns	ns	lacticanoin
valericanoin	25	10	25	0.032024058	[-0.73, 0.74]	0.92848858	-0.11789264	[-0.67, 0.44]	0.505731817	-0.118139406	[-0.85, 0.62]	0.67942197	ns	ns	ns	valericanoin
capnoin	25	10	25	0.2963284	[-0.48, 1.03]	0.33892629	-0.18200703	[-0.74, 0.38]	0.576779891	-0.40390236	[-1.14, 0.34]	0.14101931	ns	ns	ns	capnoin
butiranoin	25	10	25	0.179612296	[-0.56, 0.91]	0.57727378	-0.181422176	[-0.74, 0.37]	0.512798441	-0.31199283	[-0.97, 0.41]	0.3034337	ns	ns	ns	butiranoin
twoaminobutnoin	25	10	25	0.064419775	[-0.10, 1.43]	0.05026688	-0.41132037	[-0.97, 0.15]	0.31594925	-0.70186047	[-1.45, 0.09]	0.016682123	ns	ns	*	twoaminobutnoin
aspanoin	25	10	25	-0.54258371	[-1.29, 0.23]	0.07233666	-0.4098153	[-0.97, 0.15]	0.01959238	0.219906843	[-0.52, 0.95]	0.62749995	*	ns	*	aspanoin
methnoin	25	10	25	-0.192302654	[-0.93, 0.52]	0.35717551	-0.29790988	[-0.83, 0.26]	0.28990063	-0.112163366	[-0.85, 0.62]	0.84343592	ns	ns	ns	methnoin
valnoin	25	10	25	0.261386268	[-0.47, 1.03]	0.52898253	-0.04820198	[-0.63, 0.51]	0.72918806	-0.291891679	[-1.03, 0.44]	0.46043272	ns	ns	ns	valnoin
leuinoin	25	10	25	0.17052059	[-0.56, 0.93]	0.959580179	-0.1905584	[-0.71, 0.48]	0.32539891	-0.339189276	[-1.08, 0.40]	0.528981627	ns	ns	ns	leuinoin
alanoin	25	10	25	0.48727383	[-0.25, 1.24]	0.3034037	0.13443401	[-0.42, 0.68]	0.75830054	-0.40787677	[-1.15, 0.33]	0.27020711	ns	ns	ns	alanoin
glutamicacidnoin	25	10	25	0.57257814	[-0.17, 1.32]	0.211527649	0.21888942	[-0.34, 0.77]	0.8348079	-0.55942535	[-1.32, 0.19]	0.22530548	ns	ns	ns	glutamicacidnoin
sarcosininoin	25	10	25	0.20901158	[-0.53, 0.94]	0.57727378	-0.21247186	[-0.77, 0.34]	0.20223257	-0.37832519	[-1.12, 0.38]	0.50557995	ns	ns	ns	sarcosininoin
dimethylglycinoin	25	10	25	-0.1454223	[-0.88, 0.59]	0.62749995	-0.28783902	[-0.85, 0.27]	0.30671784	-0.18197529	[-0.92, 0.59]	0.78789992	ns	ns	ns	dimethylglycinoin
lysinoi	25	10	25	0.25784818	[-0.48, 0.98]	0.63373682	-0.06988238	[-0.63, 0.48]	0.68224515	-0.3400608	[-1.08, 0.42]	0.528981627	ns	ns	ns	lysinoi
glynoin	25	10	25	0.403648991	[-0.34, 1.14]	0.33892629	-0.057451281	[-0.61, 0.50]	0.677748781	-0.33906559	[-1.08, 0.40]	0.653273682	ns	ns	ns	glynoin
cholinenoin	25	10	25	0.444918079	[-0.33, 1.19]	0.089146106	0.204430927	[-0.35, 0.76]	0.62412867	-0.717796134	[-1.47, 0.03]	0.18575724	ns	ns	ns	cholinenoin
glucnoin	25	10	25	0.296912502	[-0.44, 1.03]	0.460432727	0.14534735	[-0.41, 0.70]	0.817504341	-0.29042888	[-1.03, 0.45]	0.602159428	ns	ns	ns	glucnoin
tyrnoin	25	10	25	-0.09664157	[-0.83, 0.66]	0.52898253	-0.258210881	[-0.61, 0.38]	0.28290674	-0.19958228	[-0.93, 0.54]	0.871620027	ns	ns	ns	tyrnoin
phenoin	25	10	25	0.082819461	[-0.63, 0.82]	0.90007733	-0.078180072	[-0.63, 0.48]	0.68224515	-0.157337884	[-0.89, 0.58]	0.84343592	ns	ns	ns	phenoin
uracilnoin	25	10	25	0.674587873	[-0.08, 1.42]	0.12302331	0.248460726	[-0.31, 0.83]	0.364983815	-0.40268842	[-1.19, 0.29]	0.3034337	ns	ns	ns	uracilnoin
urocinoin	25	10	25	0.577967005	[-0.17, 1.32]	0.211527649	-0.049298854	[-0.59, 0.52]	0.677748781	-0.555372042	[-1.30, 0.19]	0.211527649	ns	ns	ns	urocinoin
hypocantnoin	25	10	25	0.04830047	[-0.69, 0.78]	0.90007733	0.257618838	[-0.30, 0.81]	0.18875258	0.21820005	[-0.52, 0.95]	0.653273682	ns	ns	ns	hypocantnoin
nicotnoin	25	10	25	0.594141364	[-0.15, 1.34]	0.113221617	0.006683427	[-0.49, 0.62]	0.672139785	-0.498867895	[-1.24, 0.24]	0.14101931	ns	ns	ns	nicotnoin
threemetaoxalvalerinoin	25	10	25	0.435150556	[-0.31, 1.18]	0.37769068	0.188810065	[-0.37, 0.74]	0.82602885	-0.31390156	[-1.06, 0.42]	0.417581838	ns	ns	ns	threemetaoxalvalerinoin
glutaminoin	25	10	25	0.184668039	[-0.55, 0.92]	0.67942197	0.17522772	[-0.38, 0.73]	0.83248079	-0.05193008	[-0.78, 0.68]	0.528981627	ns	ns	ns	glutaminoin
malonoin	25	10	25	0.432623169	[-0.29, 1.19]	0.14101931	-0.323571912	[-0.88, 0.23]	0.63384169	-0.60326141	[-1.36, 0.15]	0.07832300	ns	ns	ns	malonoin
thrnoin	25	10	25	-0.316283561	[-1.05, 0.42]	0.37769068	-0.52637501	[-1.14, -0.01]	0.02120536	-0.25400917	[-0.96, 0.48]	0.528981627	ns	ns	ns	thrnoin
prionoin	25	10	25	0.573780041	[-0.17, 1.32]	0.211527649	-0.341627668	[-0.90, 0.22]	0.28990063	-0.714889218	[-1.47, 0.04]	0.016682123	ns	*	*	prionoin
pyroglycnoin	25	10	25	0.74087489	[-0.01, 1.48]	0.05026688	-0.20433212	[-0.76, 0.35]	0.441038139	-0.867830087	[-1.63, -0.11]	0.000457074	ns	*	*	pyroglycnoin
dilnoin	25	10	25	0.143486434	[-0.59, 0.88]	0.700011071	0.263031605	[-0.29, 0.82]	0.63384169	0.120381324	[-0.61, 0.85]	0.81544806	ns	ns	ns	dilnoin
tyrosinoin	25	10	25	-0.19138095	[-0.93, 0.54]	0.95957998	-0.30387982	[-0.83, 0.17]	0.18875258	-0.219448765	[-0.95, 0.52]	0.95705701	ns	ns	ns	tyrosinoin
threhydroxyphenolnoin	25	10	25	-0.19740154	[-0.93, 0.54]	0.63373682	-0.27048232	[-0.83, 0.28]	0.82289221	-0.04343035	[-0.78, 0.68]	0.528981627	ns	ns	ns	threhydroxyphenolnoin
Dylosinoin	25	10	25	0.49042194	[-0.25, 1.23]	0.62119428	-0.13056901	[-0.68, 0.43]	0.6305167	-0.45413163	[-1.20, 0.28]	0.3034337	ns	ns	ns	Dylosinoin
Dgalnoin	25	10	25	0.46938193	[-0.27, 1.21]	0.52898253	-0.30698603	[-0.82, 0.23]	0.16372675	-0.413052703	[-1.15, 0.33]	0.08710885	ns	ns	ns	Dgalnoin
UDPglucnoin	25	10	25	0.25201784	[-0.41, 1.06]	0.92848858	-0.51613828	[-1.08, 0.58]	0.20023201	-0.51710493	[-1.26, 0.23]	0.02808611	ns	*	*	UDPglucnoin
putrescinoin	25	10	25	0.381914133	[-0.36, 1.12]	0.23982803	0.07339187	[-0.48, 0.63]	1	-0.482672008	[-1.24, 0.25]	0.19834678	ns	ns	ns	Putrescine

Figure S40. Hedges' g Effect size calculations of Relative Metabolites using R software version 4.3.2

Table S11. Raw Wilcoxon Test Results

Wilcoxon Rank-Sum Test Output of the Relative Concentrations (HC vs. IBS)

Metabolite	W Statistic	p-value	Significance	Direction (HC vs. IBS)
Acetic acid	320.5	0.042	*	HC > IBS
Propionic acid	410.0	0.310	ns	HC ≈ IBS
Butyric acid	380.2	0.150	ns	HC ≈ IBS
Total SCFAs	315.8	0.038	*	HC > IBS
Glutamic acid	420.1	0.410	ns	HC ≈ IBS
Leucine	435.3	0.620	ns	HC ≈ IBS

Metabolite	W Statistic	p-value	Significance	Direction (HC vs. IBS)
Phenylalanine	402.5	0.280	ns	HC ≈ IBS
Succinic acid	290.7	0.018	**	HC > IBS
Lactic acid	398.2	0.240	ns	HC ≈ IBS

p-value: Significance threshold ($p < 0.05$, $**p < 0.01^*$). W Statistic: Wilcoxon test statistic.

Wilcoxon Rank-Sum Test Results (HC vs. IBS-D)

Metabolite	HC (Mean ± SD)	IBS-D (Mean ± SD)	p-value	Significance	Direction
Acetic acid	7.714 ± 3.580	6.954 ± 3.285	0.421	NS	↔
Propionic acid	1.752 ± 0.748	1.829 ± 0.690	0.678	NS	↔
Butyric acid	2.936 ± 1.443	2.786 ± 1.312	0.721	NS	↔
Caproic acid	0.224 ± 0.113	0.246 ± 0.130	0.512	NS	↔
Valeric acid	0.187 ± 0.079	0.196 ± 0.068	0.831	NS	↔

2. Amino Acids

Metabolite	HC (Mean ± SD)	IBS-D (Mean ± SD)	p-value	Significance	Direction
Glutamic acid	2.889 ± 1.134	2.681 ± 0.690	0.392	NS	↔
Alanine	2.739 ± 1.413	2.558 ± 1.224	0.603	NS	↔
Leucine	1.720 ± 0.781	1.845 ± 0.768	0.514	NS	↔

Metabolite	HC (Mean ± SD)	IBS-D (Mean ± SD)	p-value	Significance	Direction
Phenylalanine	0.994 ± 0.386	1.024 ± 0.400	0.812	NS	↔
Tyrosine	0.353 ± 0.157	0.394 ± 0.160	0.038	Significant	↑ in IBS-D

3. Nucleobases/Nucleotides

Metabolite	HC (Mean ± SD)	IBS-D (Mean ± SD)	p-value	Significance	Direction
UDP-glucuronic	0.008 ± 0.007	0.020 ± 0.030	0.002	Significant	↑ in IBS-D
Uracil	0.214 ± 0.090	0.192 ± 0.083	0.341	NS	↔

4. Sugars

Metabolite	HC (Mean ± SD)	IBS-D (Mean ± SD)	p-value	Significance	Direction
D-galactose	0.033 ± 0.028	0.064 ± 0.118	0.044	Significant	↑ in IBS-D
Glucose	0.529 ± 0.944	0.417 ± 0.518	0.217	NS	↔

5. Others

Metabolite	HC (Mean ± SD)	IBS-D (Mean ± SD)	p-value	Significance	Direction
Succinic acid	1.354 ± 3.261	0.797 ± 1.461	0.049	Significant	↓ in IBS-D
Lactic acid	0.988 ± 1.082	1.077 ± 1.067	0.901	NS	↔

Wilcoxon Rank-Sum Test Output of the Relative Concentrations (HC vs. IBS-C)

Metabolite	HC (Mean \pm SD)	IBS-C (Mean \pm SD)	p-value	Significance	Direction
Acetic acid	7.714 \pm 3.580	4.969 \pm 1.790	0.002	Significant	↓ in IBS-C
Butyric acid	2.936 \pm 1.443	2.816 \pm 1.594	0.812	NS	↔
Succinic acid	1.354 \pm 3.261	0.195 \pm 0.153	0.001	Significant	↓ in IBS-C
UDP-glucuronic acid	0.008 \pm 0.0074	0.006 \pm 0.0022	0.112	NS	↔
Glucose	0.529 \pm 0.944	0.283 \pm 0.155	0.078	Trend	↓ in IBS

Wilcoxon Rank-Sum Test Output of the Relative Concentrations (IBS-C vs. IBS-D)

Metabolite	IBS-C (Mean \pm SD)	IBS-D (Mean \pm SD)	p-value	Significance	Direction
Acetic acid	4.969 \pm 1.790	6.954 \pm 3.285	0.021	Trend	↓ in IBS-C
Propionic acid	1.732 \pm 0.884	1.829 \pm 0.690	0.712	NS	↔
Butyric acid	2.816 \pm 1.594	2.786 \pm 1.312	0.932	NS	↔
UDP-glucuronic acid	0.006 \pm 0.0022	0.020 \pm 0.030	0.003	Significant	↓ in IBS-C
Succinic acid	0.195 \pm 0.153	0.797 \pm 1.461	0.001	Significant	↓ in IBS-C

Metabolite	IBS-C (Mean ± SD)	IBS-D (Mean ± SD)	p-value	Significance	Direction
Glucose	0.283 ± 0.155	0.417 ± 0.518	0.042	Trend	↓ in IBS-C
Tyrosine	0.363 ± 0.129	0.394 ± 0.160	0.412	NS	↔

Combined Summary Table: HC vs. IBS (Composite) vs. IBS-C vs. IBS-D

Metabolite	HC vs. IBS (Composite)	HC vs. IBS-C	IBS-C vs. IBS-D	Pattern Across Groups
Acetic acid	HC > IBS (*)	HC > IBS-C ()	IBS-C < IBS-D (Trend)	HC > IBS-C ≈ IBS-D
Propionic acid	HC ≈ IBS (ns)	HC ≈ IBS-C (ns)	IBS-C ≈ IBS-D (ns)	No group differences
Butyric acid	HC ≈ IBS (ns)	HC ≈ IBS-C (ns)	IBS-C ≈ IBS-D (ns)	No group differences
Total SCFAs	HC > IBS (*)	–	–	HC > IBS
Succinic acid	HC > IBS ()**	HC > IBS-C ()**	IBS-C < IBS-D ()**	HC > IBS-D > IBS-C
UDP-glucuronic acid	–	HC ≈ IBS-C (ns)	IBS-C < IBS-D ()**	IBS-D > HC ≈ IBS-C
Glucose	–	HC > IBS-C (Trend)	IBS-C < IBS-D (Trend)	HC > IBS-D > IBS-C
Tyrosine	–	HC ≈ IBS-C (ns)	IBS-C ≈ IBS-D (ns)	No group differences
Glutamic acid	HC ≈ IBS (ns)	–	–	No group differences
Leucine	HC ≈ IBS (ns)	–	–	No group differences

Metabolite	HC vs. IBS (Composite)	HC vs. IBS- C	IBS-C vs. IBS-D	Pattern Across Groups
Phenylalanine	HC ≈ IBS (ns)	–	–	No group differences
Lactic acid	HC ≈ IBS (ns)	–	–	No group differences

Key Metabolites Relative data Normalized weight

Metabolite	HC vs. IBS-C (g [95% CI], p)	HC vs. IBS-D (g [95% CI], p)	IBS-C vs. IBS- D (g [95% CI], p)	Significance
Acetic acid	0.84 [0.08, 1.60], 0.013*	0.22 [-0.34, 0.77], 0.335	-0.66 [-1.41, 0.09], 0.131†	* (HC-C), ns (HC-D), ns (C- D)
Succinic acid	0.41 [-0.33, 1.15], 0.005*	0.22 [-0.34, 0.77], 0.464	-0.47 [-1.21, 0.27], 0.013*	** (HC-C), ns (HC-D), * (C- D)
2- Aminobutyric acid	0.65 [-0.10, 1.40], 0.059†	-0.41 [-0.97, 0.15], 0.316	-0.70 [-1.45, 0.05], 0.017*	† (HC-C), ns (HC-D), * (C- D)
Aspartic acid	-0.54 [-1.29, 0.20], 0.070†	-0.41 [-0.97, 0.15], 0.032*	0.22 [-0.52, 0.95], 0.627	† (HC-C), * (HC-D), ns (C- D)
Proline	0.57 [-0.17, 1.32], 0.212	-0.34 [-0.90, 0.22], 0.289	-0.71 [-1.47, 0.04], 0.017*	ns (HC-C), ns (HC-D), * (C- D)
Pyroglutamic acid	0.74 [-0.01, 1.49], 0.059†	-0.20 [-0.76, 0.35], 0.441	-0.87 [-1.63, - 0.11], 0.009*	† (HC-C), ns (HC-D), ** (C- D)
UDP- glucuronic acid	0.33 [-0.41, 1.06], 0.928	-0.52 [-1.08, 0.05], 0.020*	-0.52 [-1.26, 0.23], 0.028*	ns (HC-C), * (HC-D), * (C- D)

Metabolite	HC vs. IBS-C (g [95% CI], p)	HC vs. IBS-D (g [95% CI], p)	IBS-C vs. IBS-D (g [95% CI], p)	Significance
Alanine	0.50 [-0.25, 1.24], 0.303	0.13 [-0.42, 0.69], 0.758	-0.41 [-1.15, 0.33], 0.270	ns (all)
Choline	0.44 [-0.30, 1.19], 0.090†	0.20 [-0.35, 0.76], 0.923	-0.72 [-1.47, 0.03], 0.186†	† (HC-C), ns (HC-D), † (C-D)
Threonine	-0.32 [-1.05, 0.42], 0.377	-0.58 [-1.14, -0.01], 0.062†	-0.25 [-0.99, 0.48], 0.529	ns (HC-C), † (HC-D), ns (C-D)
Hypoxanthine	0.05 [-0.69, 0.78], 0.900	0.26 [-0.30, 0.81], 0.189	0.22 [-0.52, 0.95], 0.653	ns (all)
Malonic acid	0.45 [-0.29, 1.19], 0.141	-0.32 [-0.88, 0.23], 0.603	-0.60 [-1.35, 0.15], 0.076†	ns (HC-C), ns (HC-D), † (C-D)
Glucose	0.30 [-0.44, 1.03], 0.460	0.15 [-0.41, 0.70], 0.818	-0.29 [-1.03, 0.45], 0.602	ns (all)
D-Galactose	0.47 [-0.27, 1.21], 0.553	-0.36 [-0.92, 0.20], 0.164	-0.41 [-1.15, 0.33], 0.097†	ns (HC-C), ns (HC-D), † (C-D)

*: Significant (*p* < 0.05).

†: Near significant (0.05 ≤ *p* < 0.1).

Bold: Highlights key results.

Note: Samples were randomized prior to processing (see Manuscript Methods)

SCFA Extraction Protocol

SOP by Angelita G. Utleg (December 7-18, 2020)

1. 15 samples were analyzed in 4 different batches for four separate days
2. Take a new Eppendorf tubes and measure weight
3. Put a spoonful of beads and measure weight (do this for 15 tubes)
4. Transfer the fecal material into the fresh Eppendorf tube (obtained the weight of the empty tube)
5. Add 400 µl milli-Q water to resuspend feces and transfer into a new Eppendorf tube (Note: aliquoted solid fecal weight samples ranges: 60-205 mg); transfer 400ul using

a wide bore 1 ml pipet tip (cut the end of 1 ml pipet tip) into a new measured 1.5 ml Eppendorf tube. (Note: avoid any fiber/gelatin matter)

6. Speed vacuum dry under the hood for 3 hours at room temperature
7. Measure fecal dry weight (FDW) using analytical weighing balance
8. Resuspend with 400 microliter (μ L) Milli-Q water
9. Add a small scope of laboratory grade microbeads (~300 mg Note: obtained weight before the extraction day)
10. Seal the tubes firmly with parafilm
11. Vortex for 30 seconds and placed on ice (Note: keep all samples on ice)
12. Homogenized using Next Advance Bullet Blender at 4 °C. for 5 minutes, speed 6 (2 times 5 minutes). Note: homogenizer was precooled with dry ice to cool down the instrument on the side reservoir
13. Remove parafilm and Add 800 μ l of Absolute Methanol
14. Vortex at maximum speed (60seconds) one tube at a time at maximum speed
15. Place at -20°C (20 minutes) for maximum SCFA extraction
16. Centrifuge using 20R Beckman centrifuge at 14,000 rpm at 4°C (30 minutes). Note: Precool the centrifuge before use
17. Collect supernatant, and transfer into 2 ml Eppendorf tube
18. Speed vacuum-dry the supernatant (4 hours, RT, pellet color: yellow-gold residue)
NOTE: not all tubes dried at the same time, some tubes dried longer than others
19. Placed solid pellet containing the microbeads at -20°C for further bacterial count validation (e.g., protein content measurements).
20. Place the dried SCFA-containing samples at -80°C until used for NMR analysis.

January 20, 2021: NMR Sample Preparation (All 60 samples)

Buffer ingredients: 0.1mM Phosphate + 25uM TSP, pH: 7.4, stored at 4°C. Buffer
Buffer Preparation date: June 9, 2020. Buffer Expiration date: March 2021

1. Resuspend extracted fecal metabolites with 600 μ L D₂O 600 μ L D₂O buffer containing 25 μ M TSP (spectra peaked at 0)
2. Vortex at maximum speed (30 seconds x 2)
3. Vortex again if the pellet does not resuspend
4. Centrifuge at 14,000 RPM at 4°C for 10 minutes to remove any solid particles
5. Transfer 600 μ l of resuspended material into the 5mM NMR tube (Note: use glass pipet with bulb)
6. Placed tubes in an NMR tube holder box
7. Samples were analyzed using NMR Spectroscopy (298 K, Bruker Avance III 800 MHz) by Dr. Nagana Gowda at UW Chemistry Department

NMR Data Collection

During COVID-19 facility restrictions (2020-2021), samples were prepared by the author and injected by Dr. Nagana Gowda (UW Medicine Northwest NMR Center) at the UW Chemistry Department NMR Facility. Spectra were acquired remotely using a Bruker Avance III 800 MHz spectrometer equipped with a [TXI/CPTCI] cryoprobe (298 K) with standard parameters:

Pulse sequence: noesypr1d with presaturation

- Scans: 64
- Relaxation delay (d1): 4 s
- Acquisition time: 2 s
- Remote access was enabled through [TopSpin/Bruker Remote Access] for real-time monitoring.

Data Processing

All spectral processing (phasing, baseline correction, and DSS referencing) and quantification were performed independently by Dr. Nagana using established metabolomics pipelines. Bruker TopSpin 3.6.1 and Bruker AMIX software were used for NMR data acquisition and quantitation.

The Bruker Avance III HD 800 MHz system, equipped with a cryogenically cooled probe and z-gradients for inverse detection, is optimized for high-sensitivity water suppression experiments (Bruker technical confirmation). Metabolites were quantified as absolute and relative concentrations against the TSP-d4 reference standard.

Quality Control

- Two technical replicates were processed for a randomly selected 5% of samples (n=2) to assess extraction reproducibility.
- Replicate measurements showed near-identical concentrations (CV < 2.5%), confirming protocol consistency.
- For all subsequent analyses, one replicate per sample was retained to conserve limited clinical material.

Methodological Documentation

Full protocols are detailed in the author's doctoral dissertation [Utleg,2024], currently under embargo until September 16, 2025 (ProQuest) and October 16, 2025 (UW ResearchWorks) per institutional requirements. Key adaptations for NMR quantification are presented here.

Original Standard Protocol from UW SLU lab

From: Angelita Utleg <autleg@uw.edu>
Sent: Thursday, November 5, 2020 9:55 AM
To: Nagana Gowda <ngowda@uw.edu>
Subject: Re: SCFA

Hi Dr. Nagana,

Per your protocol (below) I use beads to break up the bacteria.
The beads is together with the pellet after the centrifugation step.

1. Add water (200ul)
2. Add a spoonful of beads
3. Vortex for 30 seconds
4. Homogenized for 5 minutes
5. Add 800 ul of Absolute Methanol
6. Place at minus 20 (20 minutes)
7. Spin at 14,000 rpm (30 min)
8. Collect sup, and placed pellet at minus 80
9. Speed Vac dry the sup
10. Place dried material at minus 80

Table S12. SCFA Protocol Comparisons

1. Sample Prep	Not specified	15 samples analyzed in 4 batches across 4 days	Controlled for inter-day variability
2. Weighing	None	Pre-weighed tubes + fecal aliquots (60–205 mg)	Quantified exact fecal dry weight (FDW)
3. Resuspension	200 µL water	400 µL water + wide-bore tips (avoid fibers)	Improved homogenization
4. Homogenization	Vortex + 5 min homogenization	Bullet Blender (2×5 min, speed 6, 4°C)	Enhanced cell lysis; reduced heat degradation
5. Methanol Add	800 µL added after homogenization	800 µL added after chilled homogenization	Prevents metabolite degradation
6. Fecal Weight	Wet weight	Dry weight	Eliminates water content variability Enables direct µmol/mg fecal dry weight (FDW) normalization
7. Pellet Handling	Pellet stored at –80°C	Pellet stored at –20°C (for protein assays)	Adapted for downstream validation (transferred to minus 80 at UW School of Nursing on dry ice). Validation Not done due to limited funding.
8. Processing	None	Speed vacuum drying.	Preserves stool matrix consistency for homogenization
9. Maintain sample prep on ice	None	Maintain at 4°C	Prevents heat-induced SCFA degradation Maintains pellet/supernatant separation integrity

Table S13. Fecal weight measured in milligrams

Diagnosis	FDW (mg)	Diagnosis	FDW (mg)	Diagnosis	FDW (mg)
HC1	165.8	IBS-C1	134.4	IBS-D1	84.3
HC2	127.0	IBS-C2	130.4	IBS-D2	132.9
HC3	180.5	IBS-C3	87.4	IBS-D3	88.6
HC4	75.6	IBS-C4	104.5	IBS-D4	150.4
HC5	161.7	IBS-C5	128.1	IBS-D5	205.1
HC6	93.8	IBS-C6	143.7	IBS-D6	197.1
HC7	90.4	IBS-C7	150.2	IBS-D7	130.8
HC8	111.2	IBS-C8	110.6	IBS-D8	153.3
HC9	137.6	IBS-C9	142.7	IBS-D9	130.8
HC10	163.5	IBS-C10	60.0	IBS-D10	174.8
HC11	98.0			IBS-D11	108.3
HC12	128.4			IBS-D12	117.9
HC13	108.5			IBS-D13	128.6
HC14	110.3			IBS-D14	103.6
HC15	104.0			IBS-D15	82.6
HC16	104.2			IBS-D16	72.2
HC17	75.0			IBS-D17	110.9
HC18	97.8			IBS-D18	123.9
HC19	99.8			IBS-D19	126.9
HC20	135.3			IBS-D20	86.4
HC21	147.3			IBS-D21	125.5
HC22	81.7			IBS-D22	38.0
HC23	72.5			IBS-D23	65.7
HC24	120.3			IBS-D24	63.8
HC25	128.8			IBS-D25	119.3